

PHILOLOGY

CULTURE-BOUND PROBLEMS IN TRANSLATING CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

*Turkan I.,
Dr. of Ph.in Philology
Alaviyya N.
English teacher
Nakhivan State University,*

Abstract

Unlike translators of books for adults, children's translators are in the difficult situation of combining the linguistic and cognitive abilities of a child reader with the principles of a translation theory developed mainly with adult literature in mind. It is impossible to apply these principles and methods without taking into account the development of the still immature recipient. This paper explores culture-bound problems in translating children's literature. The main focus is on the description of translations, establishing where important shifts occur and analyzing them in order to determine the relationship between source text and target text, the meaning acquired by the translated text, and its reception in the target culture.

Keywords: cultural, children, foreignization, domestication, translation.

Translating may be defined as rereading and re-writing for target-language audiences, which make translations uniquely different from their originals, every time texts are translated they take in a new language, a new culture, new readers, and a new point of view. Children's books also have a dual audience, children and adults, and sometimes a book originally intended for adults (Gulliver's travels) becomes a story written to children. A text written for children or young adults may be just as demanding in its intellectual complexity, stylistic flair or thematic content as a work for adults, as the cognitive puzzles of Lewis Carroll's Alice in Wonderland [5]. Some of the best-known international children's classics began their existence either as oral tales for all ages or as texts for adult readers and therefore include adult themes and preoccupations. Children do not think like adults, act like adults, or talk like adults. Children experience the world around them in a very different way from adults. A text suitable for children means, therefore, anything that children can understand, that interests them and meets their needs. Psycholinguists have carried out studies with respect to concreteness and abstractness of expressions [4]. According to their results small children need for concrete language with a preference for verbs taken from their daily life and many repetitions of words and sentences. Children go into the world of the story, they identify the events in the books with their own experiences. Children's literature belongs simultaneously to the literary system and the social-educational system, it is not only read for entertainment, recreation and literary experience but also used as a tool for education and socialization. Limited experience of children, translators encounter problems adapting their texts to the level of children's knowledge. Differences in culture between source text and target text have to be considered. This shows that the subject of children's literature and its translation is a very complex one and have to be taken into account [3]. Culture is defined as the combination of the ways and means of acting, thinking, feeling, perceiving reality, within which language plays a vital role. When translating, differences in cultures must be

identified in order to derive solutions in accordance with the established concept of the target text culture. It is easier to translate texts between similar cultures than those which are vastly different. This is because the languages of related cultures have similar historical roots and vocabulary, grammar, and language patterns will be similar. Another reason is the fact that a country's CHL, representative of its cultural background, is determined by pedagogic, moral and political values for children to understand and process these values, they need to be equated with familiar ideas. Creativity is named by many as important feature, as is the demand to write precisely and use expressions which are as short as possible. Frequently, literary skill is demanded, even that the translator is himself an author. On the human side translators ought to be sympathetic, sensitive and show understanding for children and their way of thinking and feeling [2]. Translators should have the ability to "feel" themselves into the language of children. They should be able to formulate their texts on a level appropriate to the respective age group addressed. Thus translators should know the language for children, but also the one of children. They should be aware of differences in style qualifications and backgrounds working in this profession [1]. Translators have to make individual decisions for each book as to whether child readers can be expected to cope with the amount of "foreignness" or whether they have to adapt somehow. In the case of a decision against localization translators have several methods available to them to offer explanations for better comprehension of the text.

"Mouse" in Azerbaijani character is a disgusting image while Mickey Mouse is a smart figure, this is from the popularity of English children's book Tom and Jerry. Some differences are so big that cannot be ignored and we cannot find suitable substitution to describe some character. Translation provides a good chance for cultural transfer to take place [3]. If the source culture and the target one have little in common, translators will face great challenges in a bid to produce a high-quality translation. Novels tend to be full of cultural items that are difficult to be dealt with during the

process of translation because they have different values or are missing in the host culture. These cultural-bound expressions need to be rendered in a way that conforms to the norms and conventions of the receptive culture especially if the target readers are children who are immature and have limited knowledge. It is clear that culture holds close connections to translation. Actually translation helps various communities to become familiar with peculiarities found in other societies. Culture occupies a major place in translation due to fact that there are some terms that have either different values in the receptor culture or do not exist at all. Such kinds of references are referred to as culture-specific terms. They can be defined as words or phrases that refer to objects and ideas familiar to a particular cultural group but not beyond. A word can indicate a positive concept in one culture, but may indicate quite the opposite in another. For instance “moon” signifies woman’s beauty for Azeri. In contrast English people associate it with paleness. Biculturalism is even more important than bilingualism as words only have meanings in terms of the cultures in which they function [2]. Cultural translation takes into consideration the vital role of the context in fleshing out the meaning. These are foreignisation and domestication translation strategies which are distinguished. The former one is aimed at preserving the strangeness of the source culture in an effort to bring it close to that of the readers [6]. However, the latter refers to the attempt to translate the source text in a transparent way. This means, minimizing the foreign culture as much as possible in order for the target text to be accessible to the target audience.

Language and Culture. Different nations are noticed to have dissimilar values, beliefs, morals, habits and behavioural conventions which seem to be transmitted from one generation to another. Consequently, it becomes apparent that many cultures exist all over the world and they vary from one place to another.

Names of mythological creatures. Children’s stories usually appear to be rich with names of strange creatures which belong to mythological sources found in various cultures. These creatures embody the most important teachings and ideas of a particular society and are intended to transfer such teachings into other generations via the power of vivid imagery. For example, according to Oxford English Dictionary (2017), a dwarf is a member of a mythical race of short, stocky human-like creatures who are usually mentioned in fantasy literature [1]. Preserving this item in the target culture will give the impression of unknown creature for the child readers and this can be a case where additional information should be provided. Nonetheless, maintaining such reference in the translated version provides the child with a golden opportunity to be open to other children’s stories that exist in totally different cultures which can make him/her learn accept the other in spite of their unfamiliarity with them.

CONCLUSION

The fact that the world consists of various cultures which vary from one another leads to facing great challenges during any form of communication among people with different cultural backgrounds.. Translating novels into different languages makes them very famous and influential. Since the source texts belong to a language and culture that hold great dissimilarities with the target ones, they are considered to be rich sources of a wide array of perplexing concepts and expressions. The translation strategies adopted to render these intricate references are examined in order to find out to what extent the translator is felicitous as a cultural mediator. Nonetheless, there may be some exotic items which appear not to be loadable with ideological messages. Consequently, they can be retained, yet they should be accompanied with some explicit clarification that will help the child readers to widen their knowledge and at the same time their attention will be drawn to the foreignness of these items. Since literary works are usually claimed to be read not only for gaining some kind of knowledge but also for entertaining and experiencing the beauty of language, translators must take these issues into their consideration while translating any piece of literary writing. Furthermore, the significance that each culture-bound expression occupies in both the source and target cultures should be determined in an attempt to help the translator identify the best solutions for rendering them.

In every translation particular information is either lost, or added, or deformed. Perfect translation is impossible because translators involuntarily bring to the translation their cultural heritage, reading experience and images, and they have different backgrounds and frames of reference. The only thing they can do is to provide that the target text is as close to the source text as possible and that the message, the atmosphere and the symbolism is retained in the target text.

References

1. Alvstad, C. (2010). Children’s literature and translation. In Y. Gambier & L. van Doorslaer (Eds.), *Handbook of translation studies*, Vol. 1, (pp. 22–27). Amsterdam: John Benjamins
2. Čermáková, A. (2015). Repetition in John Irving’s novel *A Widow for One Year*: A corpus stylistics approach to literary translation. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics* 20(3), 355–377. Amsterdam: John Benjamin
3. Grenby, M. O. & Immel, A. (2009). *Cambridge companion to Children’s Literature*. Cambridge: CU
4. Lathey, G. (Ed.). (2006). *Translation of Children’s Literature: A Reader*. Clevedon: Multilingual matters
5. Oittinen, R. (2000). *Translating for children*. London: Routledge
6. Sunderland, J. (2011). *Language, gender and children’s fiction*. London: Continuum